

An Anthropomorphic Aerial Manipulator equipped with a Testbed for Indoor Experiments

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Abstract—During interventions in hazardous environments, debris often restricts the accessibility of ground robots. When this occurs, Unmanned Aerial Manipulators (UAMs) can intervene, avoiding all of these obstacles. However, when UAMs enter and interact with such environments, designers must ensure that they possess high stability and robustness.

This work presents a teleoperated aerial manipulator for intervention in unstructured environments and a testbed to perform safely indoor experiments for evaluating the stability performance and manipulation tasks. The robot comprises an aerial platform, two arms that terminate with two Pisa/IIT Softhands, and a head equipped with stereo cameras. The testbed constrains the drone to move in a limited space and avoids that, in case of control loss, the drone falls or rambles in an indoor space, which may cause damage to the robot or humans.

Index Terms—Aerial Manipulators, Teleoperation, Testbed, Indoor Experiments

I. INTRODUCTION

The last decades have seen a stage of rapid development for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology, which is now playing an increasingly significant role in a variety of fields, such as aerial photography, agricultural monitoring, rescue search, and infrastructure inspection. In current applications, UAVs mainly serve as passive monitors, and the potential for actively interacting with the external environment is yet to be discovered.

This inspiration leads to the concept of "Unmanned Aerial Manipulators" (UAMs), which refers to UAVs equipped with robotic arms and grippers. The result is a system that combines the dexterity of UAVs with the object handling capabilities of manipulators. This concept foresees the application prospect of performing tasks in environments that are dangerous to humans or at high altitudes, such as maintenance of electrical cables and inspection of high-altitude bridges.

Many laboratories and research institutes are looking into UAMs as one of the future directions of drone and robotics development. Some overviews of related studies can be found in the literature. The authors of [1] review the development history of aerial manipulator research and assess future development trends. The design, modeling and control of UAMs are summarized in [2] and [3]. As one branch of the research, the dual-arm design has attracted researchers' attention due to its higher operational ability. Several prototypes are proposed, which can be found in [4] [5] [6].

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Fig. 1: a) Prototype of the aerial platform used for aerial teleoperation. b) Designed testbed with the aerial platform for indoor experiments

In this paper, we present an anthropomorphic aerial manipulator capable of safely interacting in unstructured environments (fig. 1a). The proposed system is used in teleoperation since we believe that human-in-the-loop intelligence can foster the performance of robots under challenging tasks. Moreover, we designed a testbed for indoor experiments (fig. 1b), which can be adjusted to fit different UAMs and used to test control algorithms safely.

II. ROBOT DESIGN

This work presents the design of an anthropomorphic aerial manipulator which comprises a flying platform (DJI MATRICE 600 PRO hexacopter), and a humanoid torso [7].

The humanoid torso consists of two 5 Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) arms equipped with two Pisa/IIT SoftHands [8] and a 2DoFs head that mounted a set of stereo cameras. The DoFs of the arm include one shoulder joint, three elbow joints, and one wrist joint, while the DoFs of the head consist of pitch and roll rotations. The arms are designed to be lightweight. The actuation motor sets are placed at the top end of the arms and actuate the joints through tendons that wrap around them. The design has the dual effect of reducing the burden on the stability and increasing the robustness in the case of accidental arms impacts. Finally, SoftHands enhances the system capability of grasping objects. Indeed, during interventions in unstructured environments, objects will not have definite shapes, thus making the use of standard grippers inadequate for grasping them. On the contrary, SoftHands adapts to the shape of the bodies under grasping, making the solution more suitable for picking up unknown objects.

The robot control is divided into two parts. The first one is related to the management of the DJI base. It considers the actions derived from the movements of the arms as coupled disturbances and is controlled to maintain the robot body's stability. The second one is related to head and arms control. They are teleoperated utilizing an Oculus device, consisting of a VR headset and a set of handles. The workspace of the robot head and arms is mapped on the workspace of the human operator wearing the Oculus device, enabling the former to follow the latter's movement trajectories. Therefore, the operator can look at the robot workspace through the stereo cameras on the head and perform complex tasks using the humanoid torso. The resulting primary advantage is the high human-in-the-loop intelligence of the system.

III. TESTBED DESIGN

Along with the design of the aerial platform, we developed a testbed for the experimental evaluation of UAM functionality in a safe indoor environment. The testbed is necessary to avoid damaging humans or the robot while testing the efficacy of the mechanical and control design. It is designed to be adjustable to adapt to different UAM prototypes and allow experiments with different controllers applied on the aerial platform.

The testbed is composed of five main components. The first is the supporting structure that maintains the system anchored to the ceiling. The second is the cage which protects the operators from accidental collisions with the drone. The other three components maintain the drone lifted while permitting a precise range of motion.

Fig. 2: Visualization of the lifting components of the experimental testbed.

Fig. 2 shows the three lifting components: the constraining structure, the weight compensator, and the load adjuster. The first component is composed of two parts. The fore is attached to the drone and is composed of two plates connected through an aluminum bar. The plates create setbacks for the motion of the drones along the z-axis. The bar passes through the latter, which is connected to the main structure and is composed of a ring that defines setbacks in roll and pitch angles and radial displacements. The weight compensator comprises two constant springs, a prismatic guide, and a cart. The cart is free

to move along the guide and is connected to the constant-force springs, designed to compensate for the extra weight added by the constraining structure. Finally, the load adjuster connects the cart to the first component of the constraining guide through cables. It is composed of a standard and a conic pulley. The latter can vary the wrapping radius in a continuous range by sliding the pulley socket using a set of worm gears.

The ultimate scope of this structure is to constrain the system in a safe space allowing it to freely test controllers while providing the minimum effects on the platform itself.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presented an anthropomorphic aerial manipulator and a testbed for safe indoor experiments. We briefly discussed the mechanical and control design of the aerial robots, composed of a DJI drone, two 5DoFs tendon-driven arms, two SoftHands, and a 2DoFs head. After that, we presented the design of a testbed for indoor experiments, which constrains the robot inside a safe space. The structure will protect the robot from falling if the system unstabilizes. While inside the safe space, the influence of the structure on the aerial platform can be ignored, making the robot work in an almost free environment. In the future, we will further investigate the efficacy of the testbed and the aerial platform.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ollero, M. Tognon, A. Suarez, D. Lee, and A. Franchi, "Past, present, and future of aerial robotic manipulators," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 2021.
- [2] F. Ruggiero, V. Lippiello, and A. Ollero, "Aerial manipulation: A literature review," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1957–1964, 2018.
- [3] X. Meng, Y. He, and J. Han, "Survey on aerial manipulator: System, modeling, and control," *Robotica*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 1288–1317, 2020.
- [4] A. Suarez, A. E. Jimenez-Cano, V. M. Vega, G. Heredia, A. Rodriguez-Castaño, and A. Ollero, "Design of a lightweight dual arm system for aerial manipulation," *Mechatronics*, vol. 50, pp. 30–44, 2018.
- [5] C. Korpela, M. Orsag, and P. Oh, "Towards valve turning using a dual-arm aerial manipulator," in *2014 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 3411–3416.
- [6] M. Perez-Jimenez, P. Ramon-Soria, B. Arrue, and A. Ollero, "Hecatonquiros: Open-source hardware for aerial manipulation applications," *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, vol. 17, no. 2, p. 1729881420921622, 2020.
- [7] F. Kong, S. Monteleone, G. Grioli, M. G. Catalano, and A. Bicchi, "A robotic aerial platform with functionally anthropomorphic arms designed for physical interaction," in *IROS - IEEE International Conference in Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2022.
- [8] M. G. Catalano, G. Grioli, E. Farnioli, A. Serio, C. Piazza, and A. Bicchi, "Adaptive synergies for the design and control of the pisa/iit soft-hand," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 768–782, 2014.